

PLATELET COUNTS IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH PREECLAMPSIA

Das Sharodiya¹

D.B.Mirzaeva²

¹ Student of International faculty, Tashkent Medical Academy, Uzbekistan

² PhD, Department of Obstetrics and gynecology, Tashkent Medical Academy, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14987019>

Introduction. Preeclampsia (PE) is a pregnancy-related complication leading to development of acute hypertensive condition that still continues to be a major concern for Obstetricians. Platelets play a key role in its pathogenesis since their activation leads to increased consumption and abnormal values, which can be used as markers of disease progression. Mean platelet volume (MPV) and platelet distribution width (PDW) are also the most important markers of platelet heterogeneity. Elevated MPV reflects the size of more active larger platelets, and elevated PDW reflects enhanced platelet heterogeneity, both of which have been linked to vascular function in preeclampsia. Although the platelet indices have been mentioned in the context of hypertensive disorders, there is still no finding of how they forecast severity and complications in PE.

The aim of this study is to assess platelet indices in preeclampsia and determine their correlation with the severity of the disease, highlighting their prognostic significance.

Materials and Methods. Study Design and Population: Case-control study was conducted at Maternity hospital 3, Tashkent Medical Academy, enrolling 58 pregnant women into: two groups. Preeclampsia group (n=28): Classified according to ISSHP criteria. Divided into mild (n=15) and severe (n=13) cases. Control group (n=30): Age-matched normotensive pregnant women without proteinuria. Platelet indices (PC, MPV, PDW) were added to CBC. Statistics were calculated using SPSS and Ms-excel.

Result. We studied the average age of patients in all study groups. The average age of patients in the main group was $27,0 \pm 2,8$, in the control group $27,2 \pm 3,7$ years ($p=0,078$). The average age of patients did not differ in the average statistical ratio. This can be concluded that hypertensive conditions of pregnant women can occur in any age category, and has no age-specific values. When studying the gestational periods of pregnant women, no statistically significant indicators ($p=0,84$) were identified. Platelet indices, namely platelet count, mean platelet volume, platelet distribution width, and plateletcrit, were evaluated in both cases and controls. None of the patients had any evidence of

thrombosis or organ damage. The PT/INR was within the normal range. Thus, all the patients included in the study had mild to moderate preeclampsia. A study of the platelet counts ($\times 10^9/l$) at different weeks of pregnancy in the examined groups revealed different indicators. The average platelet count in the main group was $270,0 \pm 11,4 \times 10^9/L$ at 20–24 weeks, $200,0 \pm 14,2 \times 10^9/L$ at 25–29 weeks and $195,5 \pm 13,9 \times 10^9/L$ at 30–34 weeks, in the control group it was $275,0 \pm 10,2 \times 10^9/L$ at 20–24 weeks, $280,0 \pm 12,5 \times 10^9/L$ at 25–29 weeks and $278,0 \pm 11,8 \times 10^9/L$ at 30–34 weeks. The platelet count was on the lower side in the patients with preeclampsia, as compared to the healthy pregnant females, however none of the patients had severe thrombocytopenia. In our study, the difference with statistically significant $p > 0,05$ was found in pregnant women at 20-24 weeks ($p = 0,08$). But Drop in platelet count in 25 to 34 weeks is significantly correlated in control and case group ($p < 0,001$).

The mean platelet volume (MPV) in pregnant women showed statistically significant signs ($p < 0,05$) at all gestational weeks of pregnancy. MPV was increased in women with preeclampsia compared to healthy pregnant women. The difference between the main group and the control group was statistically significant ($p < 0,001$). The average Mean Platelet Volume (MPV) in the main group was $11,4 \pm 0,6 fL$ at 20–24 weeks, $11,9 \pm 0,7 fL$ at 25–29 weeks and $12,1 \pm 0,6 fL$ at 30–34 weeks, in the control group it was $9,6 \pm 0,5 fL$ at 20–24 weeks, $9,8 \pm 0,6 fL$ at 25–29 weeks and $9,9 \pm 0,5 fL$ at 30–34 weeks. The correlation coefficient r had a value of $+0,42$, indicating a positive correlation. Thus, it can be assumed that the increase in MPV values is directly proportional to the increase in blood pressure. And it can be found that the longer the gestation period, the higher the MPV values in pregnant women ($p < 0,001$). Similarly, platelet distribution width (PDW) increased in preeclampsia group when compared to normotensive pregnant women ($p < 0,001$). The median value of the PDW was $16,9 fL$ in preeclampsia and $14,6$ in normotensive patients, respectively and the difference was statistically significant ($p < 0,05$), with higher values in preeclampsia.

Conclusion. The importance of the tremendous changes in the platelet indices in preeclampsia and their potential use as disease severity surrogate markers on the basis of MPV and PDW is highlighted through this study. The high coefficient of correlation with systolic BP of MPV makes it an important clinical value in predicting the vascular dysfunction to come. The study highlights the potential of platelet indices to be used as a biomarker in routine prognosis in the treatment of preeclampsia.

